

Peroxo Complexes of Molybdenum(VI), Tungsten(VI), Uranium(VI), Zirconium(IV) and Thorium(IV) Ions containing Tridentate Schiff Bases derived from Salicylaldehyde and Amino Acids

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Peroxo complexes have received considerable attention in recent years¹⁻¹⁴ because many of them are efficient stoichiometric or catalytic oxidants for organic and inorganic substrates. We have successfully employed peroxo complexes to generate glycerine from allyl alcohol which is indeed, an industrial aspect of this project⁸. However, the metal-peroxo moiety is greatly stabilised when tridentate or quadridentate auxiliary ligands are used¹⁰⁻¹⁴. We are interested in extending such a study to new peroxo com-

plexes of different elements of groups 4A and 6A containing nitrogen-oxygen donor ligands. We reported earlier a series of peroxo complexes of transition metals containing ONNO¹³ and SNNS¹⁴ Schiff bases. No attempt appears to have been made so far to isolate peroxo complexes of transition metals containing Schiff bases of amino acids. We present here the synthesis of these complexes and their possible oxygen transfer reactions. An attempt has also been made to study the size of the metal ions and the electronic

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND IR SPECTRAL (cm⁻¹) DATA OF THE COMPLEXES *

Compd./ (Colour)	Analysis % :		Ω^{-1}	ν_{OH}	$\nu_{C=O}$	$\nu_{C=N}$	$\nu_{M=O}$	$\nu_1(O-O)$	$\nu_3(M \begin{smallmatrix} \diagup O \\ \diagdown O \end{smallmatrix})$	$\nu_2(M \begin{smallmatrix} \diagup O \\ \diagdown O \end{smallmatrix})$	ν_{M-O}	ν_{M-N}
	Found/ (Calcd.)	Mol. cond.										
[Mo(O)(O ₂)(C ₉ H ₇ NO ₃)] (Yellow)	29.8 (29.9)	0			1 640	1 600	905	870	670	535	370	340
[W(O)(O ₂)(C ₉ H ₇ NO ₃)] (Grey)	44.9 (45.0)	0			1 650	1 550	930	830	640	525	380	315
[U(O)(O ₂)(C ₉ H ₇ NO ₃)] (Yellow)	51.5 (51.4)	1.5			1 645	1 570	910	815	620	520	400	270
[Zr(O ₂)(C ₉ H ₇ NO ₃).H ₂ O] (Grey)	28.4 (28.6)	1	3 400-3 500		1 650	1 600		860	665	570	370	360
[Th(O ₂)(C ₉ H ₇ NO ₃).H ₂ O] (Grey)	50.2 (50.5)	0	3 300-3 500		1 650	1 600		820	675	570	400	350
[Mo(O)(O ₂)(C ₁₃ H ₁₅ NO ₃)] (Yellow)	25.7 (25.5)	1			1 645	1 595	940	890	655	535	400	350
[W(O)(O ₂)(C ₁₃ H ₁₅ NO ₃)] (Brown)	39.5 (39.6)	0			1 645	1 550	925	880	635	530	410	340
[U(O)(O ₂)(C ₁₃ H ₁₅ NO ₃)] (Yellow)	46.0 (45.9)	2			1 645	1 560	915	860	625	520	400	295
[Zr(O ₂)(C ₁₃ H ₁₅ NO ₃).H ₂ O] (Brown)	26.0 (26.2)	1	3 200-3 500		1 640	1 580		865	660	580	410	360
[Th(O ₂)(C ₁₃ H ₁₅ NO ₃).H ₂ O] (Grey)	64.3 (64.6)	2	3 300-3 500		1 630	1 600		830	650	570	405	325
[Mo(O)(O ₂)(C ₁₆ H ₁₃ NO ₃)] (Yellow)	23.5 (23.4)	1			1 640	1 600	910	850	680	560	400	350
[W(O)(O ₂)(C ₁₆ H ₁₃ NO ₃)] (Grey)	36.7 (36.9)	0			1 645	1 570	920	830	650	540	400	340
[U(O)(O ₂)(C ₁₆ H ₁₃ NO ₃)] (Yellow)	42.8 (43.0)	2			1 640	1 580	905	820	630	520	415	370
[Zr(O ₂)(C ₁₆ H ₁₃ NO ₃).H ₂ O] (Grey)	22.1 (22.3)	1	3 100-3 500		1 660	1 580		840	690	570	420	350
[Th(O ₂)(C ₁₆ H ₁₃ NO ₃).H ₂ O] (Brown)	42.1 (42.3)	2	3 200-3 500		1 640	1 585		830	665	530	420	320

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

effect derived from the tridentate Schiff bases on the $\nu_1(\text{O}-\text{O})$ mode of the complexes in their ir spectra.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analyses and conductivity data of the complexes (1-15) are presented in Table 1. The molar conductance values show that all of the complexes are non-electrolytes in DMSO, indicating that the chelate anions are covalently bonded in all the cases. These data consistent with six-fold coordination of the metal complexes.

Ir spectral data are presented in Table 1. All the Schiff bases are potentially tridentate, coordinating at the imino nitrogen and two oxygen atoms⁴. In the complexes the appearance of $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ band (1 550–1 600 cm^{-1}) indicates coordination through the imino nitrogen atom¹⁸. This is also evident from the $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{N}}$ mode at 270–360 cm^{-1} in the far-ir spectra of the complexes^{4-11,19,20}. The disappearance of ν_{OH} band (3 400–3 500 cm^{-1}) in the complexes^{1,2,3-8,11-13} indicate deprotonation at the OH end, thus providing oxo coordination. That the ligands deprotonate at the OH end is also evident from the appearance of $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{O}'}$ modes (O' = oxygen in organic ligands) at 370–420 cm^{-1} in the far-ir spectra of the complexes⁴⁻¹¹. All the complexes display $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ modes at 1 625–1 650 cm^{-1} characteristic of carboxylate binding^{4,6,11}. The complexes 1-3, 6-8, 11-13 show diagnostic bands at 905–940 cm^{-1} attributable to $\nu_{\text{M}=\text{O}}$ modes^{4,7,8,11,13}. The complexes 4, 5, 9, 10, 14 and 15 show broad bands at 3 400–3 500 cm^{-1} due to coordinated water molecules. The metal-peroxo grouping (local C_{2v} symmetry) gives rise to three ir and Raman-active vibrational modes. These are predominantly O–O stretch (ν_1), the symmetric M–O stretch (ν_2) and antisymmetric M–O stretch (ν_3). The characteristic $\nu_1(\text{O}-\text{O})$ modes of the complexes 1-15 appear at 815–890 cm^{-1} . In particular, the ν_1 mode decreases upon passing from molybdenum complexes (1, 6 and 7) to the corresponding tungsten complexes (2, 6 and 12) and then further decreases for uranium complexes (3, 8 and 13). Again in the case of the peroxo complexes of the elements of group 4A, there is a decrease in ν_1 mode upon passing from Zr complex (4, 9 and 14) to the corresponding Th complexes (5, 10 and 15). The present study thus clearly reveals that for the $\text{M}(\text{O}_2)$ grouping, the $\nu_1(\text{O}-\text{O})$ modes decrease with an increase in the atomic number of the metals in a particular group. The present peroxo complexes display ν_3 and ν_2 modes at 615–690 and 520–570 cm^{-1} respectively.

The peroxo complexes of molybdenum, tungsten, uranium, zirconium and thorium are not explosive. So that the possible reactivity of the present peroxo complexes toward olefinic compounds could be explored. The present peroxo complexes are all found to be inert towards oxidation of olefin and other substrates like triphenyl phosphine or

triphenyl arsine. These negative results outline the enhanced stability of the metal-peroxo moiety in the presence of tridentate dinegative chelating ligands, which precludes oxygen transfer reactions. We also observed a similar stabilising effect of the peroxo complexes containing various multidentate ligands^{4-6,10-11}.

Experimental

All chemicals used were reagent grade (E. Merck and B.D.H.) and were used as supplied.

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on an Acculab 10 spectrophotometer. Conductivities in 10^{-3} M DMSO solutions were measured at 25° using a WPA CMD-400 conductivity meter. Metals were determined gravimetrically¹⁵.

The Schiff bases : An amino acid (glycine, leucine or phenylalanine) (0.01 mol) together with KOH (0.56 g, 0.01 mol) in water (50 ml) was stirred for 1 h on a water-bath at 50–60° to get a clear solution. Then salicylaldehyde (1.22 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was added to it and the mixture was again heated for 2–3 h on a water-bath at 50–60° when a clear yellow solution was obtained. Several attempts to solidify the Schiff bases failed. Therefore, the Schiff bases were used *in situ*^{16,17} for the synthesis of the peroxo complexes.

Preparation of complexes 1, 2, 6, 7, 11 and 12 : $[M(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)L] M = \text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}$ or W^{VI} , $L = \text{a dinegative Schiff base}$. *General method* : A suspension of MO_3 (0.01 mol) in 30% H_2O_2 (60 ml) was stirred overnight at 45–50° to get a clear solution. This was cooled and to the cold solution was added the previously prepared Schiff bases. The resulting solid products were washed successively with water and ether and dried *in vacuo* over P_4O_{10} (yields 55–65%).

Preparation of complexes 3, 8 and 13 ($[U(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)L]$). *General method* : To a cold solution of $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (5.0 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was added successively the previously prepared cold solution of the Schiff bases and 30% H_2O_2 (30 ml). The resulting yellow solid products were washed with water and ether and dried *in vacuo* over P_4O_{10} (yields 60–70%).

Preparation of complexes 4, 5, 9, 10, 14 and 15 ($[M(\text{O}_2)L \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}] M = \text{Zr}^{\text{IV}}$ or Th^{IV}). *General method* : $\text{M}(\text{NO}_3)_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.01 mol) in water (30 ml) was added to a cold solution of the previously prepared Schiff base followed by the addition of (40 ml) of 30% H_2O_2 and the mixture was cooled in ice. The resulting solid products were washed with water and ether and then stored as before (yields 50–65%).

All the complexes were further purified by reprecipitation from DMSO before drying.

Attempted reactions of 1, 3-5, 7, 8, 10 and 14 : Refluxing 1 and 4 with allyl alcohol in a 1:1 molar ratio in tet-

rahydrofuran (THF) medium for 48 h failed to produce any reactions, 1 and 4 being recovered unchanged. Similar negative results were also obtained by (i) refluxing 7 with allyl alcohol in the presence of a large excess of 30% H₂O₂ in dioxane medium for 48 h at 90°, (ii) refluxing 10 and 14 with equimolar quantities of triphenyl phosphine in THF for 48 h and (iii) refluxing of 3, 5 and 8 with equimolar quantities of triphenyl arsine in THF for 48 h.

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